

Rijpfjorden observatory data sets

One part of the dataset has been published on NIRD (Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data) – Research Data Archive, the other part on the Arctic Data Centre (ADC) by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute. The links below link directly to the datasets. The datasets published in the ADC can also be accessed by the umbrella collection with DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.21343/FW8Z-3917>

2006-2007

<https://doi.org/10.21343/BE2A-7929>

2007-2008

<https://doi.org/10.21343/3B8W-NM43>

2008-2009

NO DATA due to heavy sea ice (no re-deployment possible after 2008 recovery)

2009-2010

<https://doi.org/10.21343/287K-AF44>

2010-2011

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00026>

2011-2012

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00027>

2012-2013

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00025>

2013-2014

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00023>

2014-2015

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00018>

2015-2016

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00019>

2016-2017

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00020>

2017-2018

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00017>

2018-2020 (no recovery in 2019 due to ice conditions, continuous 2-yr deployment)

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00031>

2020-2021

<https://doi.org/10.21343/F6JS-6H61>

2021-2022

<https://doi.org/10.21343/MBVT-Q102>

2022-2023

<https://doi.org/10.21343/7E90-G196>

2023-2024

<https://doi.org/10.21343/TEFQ-BN41>